

ABSTRACT

This article examines the issues of improving the maintenance and diagnostic system of belt conveyors operating at the Angren coal mine. The reliability and operational efficiency of belt conveyors directly depend on the quality of maintenance organization. During operation, various types of wear, deformation, and malfunctions occur in rollers, belts, drums, and tensioning mechanisms. Therefore, when planning maintenance activities, it is recommended to apply a preventive approach based on diagnostic measurement results. The article presents parameters characterizing the technical condition of belt conveyors, elements of the diagnostic system, and recommendations for adapting them to the operating conditions of the Angren coal mine.

KEYWORDS:

belt conveyor, maintenance, diagnostics, monitoring, reliability, tension, roller load, Angren coal mine, SCADA.

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LITERATURE ANALYSIS ON INCREASING THE CLEANING EFFICIENCY OF AIR FILTERS OF MACHINES USED IN MINING ENTERPRISES

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ABSTRACT

The article provides essential information about the contamination of air filters in mining machines used at mining enterprises, meaning the reduction in operational efficiency caused by dust or other airborne particles and their negative impact on the machine’s performance. In addition, a scientific analysis of the literature aimed at improving the efficiency of air filter cleaning systems used in today’s mining industry of our country is presented. In addition, the research methodology section of the article scientifically substantiates the issues of improving the process of effective air filter purification using the method of theoretical analysis, the method of mathematical modeling, and the methods of

experimental tests. The article thoroughly analyzes the air filters currently used in mining machines and proposes the use of an improved filter cleaning device to improve the filter cleaning process.

KEY WORDS

air filters, cleaning, pressure, filter cleaning device, filter cleaning coefficient, internal combustion engine.

INTRODUCTION

Today, the most widely used engines in mining and transport vehicles that are directly involved in the extraction, loading and delivery of minerals to enrichment plants in mining enterprises are internal combustion engines. Due to the high dust content in open-pit mining facilities, i.e. quarries, the air filters of mining machines used in quarries become clogged with dust particles much faster than expected, so cleaning the air filters of machines used in the mining industry is one of the most urgent issues today.

The continuous, reliable and high-performance operation of the internal combustion engine of mining machines directly depends on the purity of the amount of air supplied to it and the quality of the filtered air flow, which proves the need for constant, systematic cleaning of air filters. Therefore, improving the timely and high-quality cleaning devices for mining machine air filters, ensuring the performance, efficiency, and long-term operation of not only air filters, but also the internal combustion engine and mining machines, is one of the urgent problems of today.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS

Today, many researchers and scientists are conducting a number of scientific studies on the issues of improving the air filter cleaning systems of mining machines, updating the design of filters, increasing their service life. The long-term operation of mining machines and internal combustion engines is a quantity that depends on many external and internal factors. Today, there are many modern methods of cleaning air filters, and cleaning air filters of mining machines is carried out at the repair sites or equipment service facilities of every large giant enterprise [1].

Nowadays, many foreign researchers and scientists are conducting scientific research on the improvement of air filter cleaning systems for mining vehicles, including: Marius Tomaa, Jordan Filerua, Peyyang Li, Yatsek A. Koziel, Nubia Macedo, Jeffrey J. Zimmerman, Danielle Wrzesinski, Erin Sobotka, Mateo Balderas, William B. Waltz, Reed Vincent Paris, Myongson Li, Dongjie Liu, Bauyrjan Yedilbayev, Brett C. Ramirez and William S. Jenks. Despite the ongoing scientific research and experiments, the problems of improving air filter cleaning systems have not been fully resolved to this day [2].

On the issues of improving air filters for mining vehicles, scientists of our republic, such as Bozorov B.I., Abdurashidov A.A. and others, have also conducted many scientific research and studies, prepared experimental test stands and achieved good results [3].

Despite the many results achieved on the basis of numerous scientific researches and experiments conducted by foreign and domestic scientists, cases of various types of dust particles entering the internal combustion engines of mining machines used in mining enterprises today, and their negative impact on the performance of internal combustion engines, as well as cases of damage and failure of engines due to dust, are observed in the mining industry. Taking into account the above, the article aims to address the issues of improving the air filter cleaning system of mining machines and to determine the tasks for scientific research based on analytical analysis [4].

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Air filter cleaning systems for mining machines serve as the basis for increasing the efficiency and ensuring long-term, reliable operation of internal combustion engines. Scientific research and scientific-practical research on the improvement of air filter cleaning systems are carried out on the basis of a wide variety of methodological approaches, below we will analyze the main types of research methodologies currently being conducted [5]:

1. Theoretical analysis method - in this method, it is necessary to analyze the literature analysis and foreign and local scientific researches, articles and theses, as well as the data collected on the topic. In this section, the methods and possibilities of cleaning the air system entering the engine in order to protect the internal combustion engine of mining machines from various types of dust are studied and analyzed.

2. Mathematical modeling method - in this methodological method, it is possible to use a number of mathematical methods for cleaning the air filters of mining machines in the object of scientific research and the loss of air pressure supplied to it, as well as the nominal values of air speed.

3. Experimental research method - in this method, an experimental test stand is prepared to conduct scientific research to improve the cleaning efficiency of mining machinery dust filters and improve the methods of cleaning filters from dust. We can determine the effectiveness of increasing the cleaning efficiency of filters from dust through several types of tests:

- the method of comparing the initial mass of the filters and the masses after cleaning;
- resistance of the filters to the applied pressure before cleaning and resistance to the pressure after cleaning is measured;
- the method of determining the dust capacity, surface, porosity and filter size on the surface of the filter and several other methods.

Taking into account that the combined and generalized application of the above research methods

increases the scientificity and reliability of the research work, we conducted a scientific research study in the article using theoretical analysis and mathematical modeling methods [6].

DISCUSSIONS AND RESULTS

Today, the process of cleaning air filters of transport vehicles, mainly used in open-pit mining

enterprises, is organized at each facility in order to increase the efficiency of the enterprise. Figure 1 below shows a device for cleaning the air filters of mining vehicles using a compressor and cleaning the dust coming out of the filter with an additional fan device located behind, but this method shows that the air filters are poorly cleaned.

(a) filters used in mining

(b) filter cleaning device in the factory

Figure 1. Air filter cleaning device for air filters used in mining enterprises

Based on the research and experiments conducted, we can say that cleaning air filters only by blowing air with a compressor reduces the cleaning efficiency of these filters by an average of 30-40%, and the cleaned filters are clogged with dust again, and their operating time is very short [7].

According to the analysis of the literature and taking into account the above indicators, we propose an experimental test device for cleaning air filters with a special rotary and reciprocating motion for cleaning air filters of mining machines:

a) mining machine air filter

b) special filter cleaning device offered

Figure 2. Mining machine air filter and proposed device for cleaning it

Due to the fact that air filters currently used in mining enterprises operate at very low efficiency levels and the very low cleaning coefficient of this device, a new, more efficient filter cleaning device, shown in Figure 2, has been proposed.

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

Nowadays, the cleaning devices used in the filter cleaning areas of mining enterprises for cleaning air

filters of mining machines are mainly used in the air spraying, dust suction and rotary motion of the filters. The filter cleaning device we offer is an effective device with higher efficiency and reliability than existing filter cleaning devices, as a result of preventing the loss of air pressure from the compressor during filter cleaning and providing additional vibration.